

VALUE4FARM

D2.5 Protocol of good practices for handling existing residual crop streams and digestate use

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AD	Anaerobic Digestion
BMP	BioMethane Potential
CSTR	Continuously Stirred Tank Reactor
DM	Dry Matter
EBA	European Biogas Association
EO	Expected Outcome
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GIE	Gas Infrastructure Europe
HRT	Hydraulic Retention Time
INA	Inagro
NH ₃	Ammonia
NWE	North West Europe
O	Objective
OM	Organic Matter
OOC	Open Online Course
ROI	Return On Investment
VeDoWS	Vermeulen Dobbelaere Welfare System
VS	Volatile Solids

KEYWORDS LIST

- Crop residues
- Manure
- Anaerobic digestion
- Biomethane production
- Digestate
- Good practices

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The overall objective of VALUE4FARM is to demonstrate the effectiveness, sustainability and replicability of three renewable-based local value chains coupling sustainable food production and renewable-energy production to contribute to the reduction of fossil energy use in the agricultural sector by matching local needs in terms of electricity, heat, mobility, residual bioresources and land management. A critical way of achieving this is by providing clear and hands-on information to end-users, such as protocols describing how to implement these renewable-based local value chains on the farm. Specifically, in Belgium, the main focus lies on the adoption of Anaerobic Digestion (AD) and subsequent biomethane production, by which agricultural residues - such as crop waste or manure - can be valorised by producing on-farm energy, providing electricity, heat or even tractor fuel. Implementing a comprehensive protocol tailored to the unique needs of the Flanders region but applicable in other European countries also serves as a blueprint for sustainable energy production while addressing local agricultural challenges.

Several biomass residue types which are not routinely valorised yet were identified, including (hydro)leek, horticultural waste (tomato, cucumber, bell pepper), chicory residues and manure. These residual biomass streams can be suitable substrates for biogas production since they have an almost year-round availability. Some of these streams - such as chicory roots, top leaves of leek, or fresh manure - also show a good biogas potential compared to other known substrates. However, it should be noted that for some other streams, the biogas potential is rather low, *e.g.* leek roots, chicory leaves, old manure, ... Additionally, some logistic challenges might arise when collecting these residues, such as metal and plastic clips used in horticulture. Therefore, a thorough SWOT analysis was performed assessing the potential for these residual biomass streams.

For some residues, AD seems difficult at first sight, but co-digestion could offer a solution. For instance, chicory leaves alone have a very low biogas potential due to the low Dry Matter content. Still, it could be a good co-substrate for VeDoWS manure, which is the solid fraction of pig manure after primary separation. This type of manure contains a high proportion of organic matter, but it is too dry to be used alone in a classic AD plant. Therefore, mixing it with a wet co-substrate such as chicory residues could be a good solution to valorise both streams.

This document also contains practical guidelines for farmers wanting to invest in AD. It provides an overview of the most important factors influencing the return on investment, such as the number of available agro residue types and their biogas potential, the amount of green energy that can be produced, the investment cost and the most important yearly revenues and costs. By following the necessary tools, farmers can assess the profitability of AD.

The digestate, the remaining biomass after AD, can be used on-farm as a fertiliser again. This product contains most of the nutrients already available in the substrate but in a more mineralised form, making it more readily available for crop uptake. It is important to highlight that good practices should be followed, such as performing a detailed analysis of the product, since a wide range of different digestate products are available. Furthermore, it is advisable to follow the 4R principle of sustainable fertilisation,

including using the Right fertiliser, at the Right moment, with the Right dose and the Right fertilisation technique.

To conclude, some handy tips & tricks are provided for farmers, providing insights into different methods to desulphurise and dewater the biogas, which are important actions to be taken to increase the life span of the installation and to avoid contamination of the biogas. Furthermore, it also mentions the importance of good feeding and mixing practices, how to control foam formation, good temperature regimes, and the importance of consuming as much of the produced energy on the farm as possible. Last, but not least, it is highlighted that taking the necessary safety measures is of utmost importance.

In essence, this document provides hands-on information on the AD of agro residues and equips farmers and other stakeholders with the knowledge to valorise unused residual biomass streams as energy, making sure to close energy and nutrient loops. Although this deliverable mainly focuses on residual biomass streams in Flanders, the practical guidelines and tips & tricks are applicable in other European countries as well. Furthermore, other residual biomass streams of interest can easily be added to this document. Using this approach, Value4Farm will contribute to paving the way for a greener, more resilient future in farming practices.

1. INTRODUCTION

The overall objective of VALUE4FARM is to demonstrate the effectiveness, sustainability and replicability of three renewable-based local value chains coupling sustainable food production and renewable-energy production to contribute to lowering the use of fossil energy from the agricultural sector by matching local needs in terms of electricity, heat, mobility, residual bioresources and land management. The overall objective is complemented by four clear, realistic, measurable, and verifiable objectives (Os) outlined in Table 1.

Table 1: Objectives of Value4farm project (Objectives supported by D2.5 are circled in red)

Objective	Description
O1	Development of sustainable agricultural protocols, compatible with renewable energy production and farmers' specifications
O2	Proposing a wide range of renewable energy production and storage technologies, meeting farmers' residue management, electricity, heat and mobility needs
O3	Validation of the sustainability and circularity of three renewable-based local value chains through demonstration
O4	Ensuring the replicability and widespread use of the demonstrated overall value chains

This deliverable is primarily linked to O1, developing sustainable agricultural protocols that are compatible with renewable energy production and farmers' specifications. Since this protocol (D2.5) will focus on handling already existing residual crop streams and usage of digestate, it will only focus on AD technology. The other protocols developed within Value4Farm for the Mediterranean (D2.4) and Atlantic (D2.3) region will also focus on agrivoltaics, combining food and energy production in the same field via photovoltaic panels.

More specifically, this deliverable will focus on valorising agricultural residues, which is inevitable in standard farming practices. Certain crops produce a lot of biomass that is not consistently put to good use. Therefore, the idea behind the development of this protocol is to deal with such side streams, focusing on existing residual streams which, at the moment, are not valorised while being present in high volumes. For instance, in Flanders alone, the leek production and climbing vegetables in greenhouses produce a lot of non-exploited residual bioresources, representing, for instance, a lost biomethane and fuel potential. Also in other European countries residual biomass streams are widely available and can potentially serve as feed for AD plants. With all the current attention towards circularity - supported by, amongst others, the Circular Economy Action Plan - it is essential to look at options from which both farmers and society benefit by reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) and ammonia (NH₃) emissions, minimising nutrient leaching, and increasing income and self-sufficiency in terms of energy. Hence, the Value4Farm project aims to develop novel renewable-based local value chains for energy production. Two renewable-based local value chains assessed within Value4Farm are Anaerobic Digestion (AD) and agrivoltaics.

While growing extra crops to generate energy can be of interest in certain areas, it is important to highlight that food has a higher value than energy, as depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The biobased value pyramid (Stegmann et al., 2020)

The food vs fuel debate is intense, especially in regions with expensive agricultural fields, such as North West Europe. For instance, in Flanders, the average cost of 1 hectare of agricultural land is 64,377 EUR, more than six times the European average (Verstraete, 2024). In these regions, it makes more sense to focus on the good use of agricultural side streams. Therefore, this Value4Farm protocol will look into the valorisation of agro residues via AD and subsequent biomethane production. In doing so, paying attention to the end users' needs and the regulatory framework is important. Hence, this deliverable considers the outcomes of D1.1 (Report on farmers' needs and decision support tool framework) and D1.3 (Report on regulation framework analysis), translating scientific and regulatory outcomes into a clear and straightforward protocol that is easily consultable for farmers and farm advisors. This will reduce agriculture's carbon footprint from its own energy consumption and agricultural waste management (EO 2) and increase sustainability and circularity in agriculture while positively impacting biodiversity (EO 3).

2. WHAT ARE THE FARMERS' NECESSITIES?

As part of WP1, a survey was dispatched to European farmers to probe their needs related to and interest in renewable energy technologies. In addition, Focus Group discussions were set-up in the demonstration and replication countries to define any concerns and further finetune these needs. These outcomes set the baseline for the farmers' specifications towards renewable energy integration in agriculture. It could be noted that out of the 170 survey respondents, 11% already produce gas from bio-energy. Almost 58% of survey respondents said they were considering investing in energy diversification on their farms in the next five years. Of these respondents, farmers in Italy appeared to be the most inclined towards considering energy diversification, with 83% confirming their intent in the survey. Of all the participants interested in investing in various types of on-farm energy production, biogas was the second with 40% interest. This interest was in all participating countries, but again, the highest in Italy.

These results make it clear that biogas can become an important renewable energy source soon and that farmers are willing to learn more about this technology and implement it on their own farms. However, they highly value a personal understanding of the technology and easily available information and support. Therefore, protocols should be very hands-on and provide easy and accessible information. Farmers indicated that information on diverse crop rotations was the most important stated potential area of training needs, followed by agrivoltaics and AD. The preferred formats for providing training and knowledge are via in-person workshops/demonstrations. Also, online workshops/demonstrations and videos were rated highly.

The Focus Group Discussions revealed that farmers already see the multiple benefits of AD, such as agroresidues valorisation and circular energy production. The opportunity for biogas production to make full use of waste streams or facilitate diversification of cropping for feedstock may also have additional environmental benefits. On-farm energy production was also seen as beneficial regarding the security of energy supply. However, they have concerns about unclear and sometimes uncertain legislative frameworks, the potential competition with hydrogen as an alternative renewable gas, labour intensity, permit difficulties and the need for qualitative input streams. Furthermore, participants expressed a need for decision support tools, seminars, and accessible information to implement the Value4Farm technologies, such as AD. They emphasised the challenge of staying informed amidst rapidly evolving technologies, policies, and markets. They sought clear planning, 1-on-1 guidance, and incentives for energy production. Hence, this protocol will provide hands-on information about the operation of a farm-scale biogas plant, so the concerns of farmers can be minimised and they can easily access information on it. As part of other WPs, several open demo days and in-person workshops will be organised later on in the project.

Figure 2: Focus Group discussion in Belgium on on-farm AD production

Adapting crop rotations was highlighted as a tool to maintain food/animal feed production while incorporating energy crops and utilising crop wastes to support soil health. A key message was to keep rotational suggestions as flexible as possible and closely aligned with existing knowledge in a region. Therefore, introducing completely novel crops and rotations in addition to the expectation of the farmer to adopt new energy technologies will heighten the adoption barrier. This is one of the main reasons this protocol does not incorporate new crops but focuses on already existing residual biomass streams.

Furthermore, the EU is supporting biogas and biomethane production via the Biomethane Action Plan - as part of the RePowerEU plan - aiming for 35 billion m³ biomethane production by 2030 in Europe. Individual Member States have different targets in their National Energy and Climate Plans. Consequently, support measures for AD and biomethane production can differ significantly. The full results of these outcomes are available in D1.1 (Report on farmers' needs and decision support tool framework) and D1.3 (Report on regulation framework analysis).¹

¹ <https://value4farm.eu/resources/>

3. LOCAL ANALYSIS OF AVAILABLE BIOMASS IN FLANDERS

When looking at valorisation via AD and subsequent biomethane production, potential crops of interest should ideally be available year-round, have a sufficient biogas potential and be logistically easy to handle. Some potential interesting agroresidues were identified already during the project preparation (**Fout! Verwijzingsbron niet gevonden.**).

Table 2: Crops of interest already identified during the project proposal preparation (copied from the project proposal)

Crop	Area in Flanders (ha) ²	Type of residual stream	Amount (t/ha) ^{3,4}	Total (t/y)	Dry matter (%)	Biogas potential (Nm ³ /t) ⁵	Organic dry matter (%)	Maximal biomethane production (Nm ³ /y)
Leek	2,970	Top leaves	15	44,550	12	119	85	5,513,508
		During cleaning	11	32,670				
Tomato	599	Stems	30-50	18,000-50,000	20	60	N.A.	530,989 (fresh matter)
		Fruits	10	5,990				
Bell pepper	106	Stems	25	2,650		60	N.A.	116,324 (fresh matter)
		Fruits	6	636				
Cucumber	46.5	Stems	25	1,162	20	60	N.A.	41,135 (fresh matter)

Based on the outcomes of the Focus Group Discussions in Work Package 1 and progressing insights taking into account in the first place availability and continuity, additional residual biomass streams were identified, such as chicory residues. Additionally, manure is seen as an interesting source because of

² Analysis of the Most Recent Parcel Declaration. Departement L&V, 2021

³ Agneessens et al. (2014). Onderzoek Naar Het Beheer Van Oogstresten Bij Vollegrondsgroenten En Mogelijkheden Van Vanggewassen En Teeltrotaties Met Het Oog Op De Waterkwaliteitsdoelstellingen Van Het Actieprogramma 2011-2014 (MAP4). VLM

⁴ Kips et al. (2017). Characterization And Processing Of Horticultural Byproducts: A Case Study Of Tomato And Belgian Endive Roots, PhD thesis, UGent

⁵ Maximaal Productiepotentieel Van Biomethaan In Vlaanderen Uit Biomassareststromen. TransBio project, D3.4A, 2018

the intensity of animal husbandry in Flanders. Also, co-digestion of manure and crop residues can be a potentially interesting energy source for biogas production. The next paragraphs will outline the availability of each of these side streams.

3.1. (HYDRO)LEEK RESIDUES

Leek is a crop that can be grown almost all year round and is very common in Belgium, being responsible for about 20% of the total European production (Eurostat, 2024). Because of its almost continuous production, it is an interesting crop to assess for biogas production. There are two residual streams during the production of leek: top leaves and roots. However, the current machinery is not intended to harvest roots. Consequently, these residues stay incorporated into the soil and are not available.

Based on data collected in the WikiLeeks project⁶, the average gross production is 66.5 tonnes/ha and the average net production 43.4 tonnes/ha. In other words, approximately 1/3 of the gross production is considered waste (top leaves + peeling residues). In 2022, Belgium had 3,780 ha of leeks (Eurostat, 2024), meaning that the yearly gross production was approximately 251,370 tonnes. Consequently, the yearly amount of top leaves and peeling residues available in Belgium is around 80,000 tonnes. There is a production peak in Autumn and Winter, but in general there is a year-round continuous biomass stream (T. De Cuyper, personal communication, 28 March, 2024).

Figure 3: Leek residues

Furthermore, INA is also looking into hydroleek production, exploiting an innovative hydroponic system (Figure 4). This system has a higher production and residual streams per ha. Hydroleeks is not yet found

⁶ <https://inagro.be/projecten/wikileeks-preciezer-prei-telen-met-precisielandbouw>

in practice in Flanders, but it is expected that some systems will be operational by 2025-2026. However, INA already calculated the potential yield based on its own experience. It can be concluded that there would be a yearly gross production of 488 tonnes/ha. This higher production than ground leeks is because there are multiple annual cultivation rounds, and the crops are closer to each other. On top of that, 75 tonnes/ha clean roots will become available. Out of the 488 tonnes/ha gross production, 339 tonnes can be sold on the market, while 149 tonnes are considered as waste (of which about 2/3 consists of top leaves and 1/3 out of peel waste (T. De Cuypere, personal communication, 28 March, 2024)). An additional big advantage of residual biomass waste from hydroleeks is that no inorganic material exists. Hence, it is not contaminated with soil and sandy particles, requiring fewer cleaning steps, which is also beneficial for the biogas facility since inorganic material needs to be removed as much as possible before entering the reactor.

Figure 4: Hydroleek facility at INA, Belgium

3.2. HORTICULTURAL RESIDUE STREAMS

In horticultural greenhouse production, many residual streams can become available, mainly consisting of leaves and stalks. It is estimated that greenhouses cover an area of 55,000 ha in Europe, with the Netherlands, Spain, Italy, France and Germany as main producers. Three crops of interest have been identified: tomatoes, cucumbers, and bell peppers.

According to Eurostat (2024), there was a cultivated area of 640 ha tomatoes, 90 ha cucumbers and 130 ha bell peppers in Belgium in 2022, equalling a production of 298,800 tonnes of tomatoes, 34,920 tonnes of cucumbers and 35,100 tonnes of bell peppers. All crops have similar residual streams that become available throughout the year, *i.e.* leaves that become available more or less continually and a combination of stalks and leaves that become available in bulk after each harvest. However, it should be noted that this last stream is often contaminated with plastic or metal clips and strings. Nevertheless, there is increasing attention towards biobased clips and strings. For instance, the Flemish project Zero Waste⁷ is looking into solutions for the high waste processing costs by screening alternative options. Additionally, an extra stream of vegetables does not meet the selling requirements and can come available as AD feedstock. For instance, this could be 600 cucumbers per hectare per day.

Figure 5: Tomato growing in a greenhouse

⁷ [ZERO WASTE: Zero waste approach voor vruchtgroenten onder glas | Inagro](#)

Growers are looking into alternative valorisation pathways for the 30 - 50 tonnes per hectare tomato waste (equalling yearly 19,200 - 32,000 tonnes in total in Belgium), the 25 - 30 tonnes per hectare for cucumber (equalling yearly 2,250 - 2,700 tonnes) and the 40 tonnes per hectare for pepper bells (equalling yearly 5,200 tonnes). The almost continuous stream of leaves (in total, about 1-2 tonnes/ha) is mostly being composted nowadays, while a waste processor is processing the bulk stream at the end of the harvest. This extra cost goes up to 150 - 196 EUR per tonne. For tomatoes, there is only one growing cycle per year, hence one bulk stream of residual biomass. For cucumbers, there are normally three growing cycles throughout one year, with harvest at the end of April, the beginning of August and the beginning of November, and a 'rest' period between November and half of January. For bell peppers there is only one growing cycle per year (mostly from December until October). The continuous biomass stream (leaves) is lower for this vegetable. Most of it becomes available at the end of the growing cycle (S. Craeye, personal communication, 6 March, 2024).

3.3. CHICORY RESIDUES

In Europe, there is a total area of about 40,000 ha dedicated to chicory production, of which more than 25% is located in Belgium. The total European production is about 1,200,000 tonnes, of which 556,200 tonnes is produced in Belgium (Eurostat, 2022). The cultivation of chicory can occur continuously throughout the year, with the lowest production during summer and the highest production during Autumn and Winter. Cultivation of chicory releases many relatively stable residual flows in the form of roots and leaves: producing 1 kg of chicory releases about 10-18% waste in the form of leaves and 125-166% in the form of roots (Primalof, personal communication, 21 June, 2023). Extrapolated on a total chicory production of 556,200 tonnes, this means, on an annual basis 55,620-100,116 tonnes of leaves and 695,200-923,292 tonnes of roots. Currently, the roots are already (partly) valorised as feed for cattle farmers in the region. However, feed schedules are becoming more and more precise, potentially complicating this marketing. For the leaves, no valorisation is possible at present. Growers are especially interested in alternatives for this residual biomass stream.

Figure 6: Chicory roots

Additionally, there is a relatively constant but large energy demand on hydro farms due to, among other things, the cooling of roots, with an average electricity consumption of 200-300 kWh/year per tonne of chicory roots. However, this is highly dependent on various factors, such as the efficiency of the cooling installation. This constant energy demand corresponds to the energy production profile of an AD plant. In other words, farm-scale AD can ensure that such residual streams are utilised on the farm for their own renewable energy generation. In Flanders, the Operational Group ChicoryRePowered is working on valorising chicory residual biomass streams via AD⁸.

3.4. MANURE

In the European Union, animal farming generates annually more than 1.4 billion tonnes of manure (Königer et al., 2021). This is a valuable resource that can be used as a fertiliser. However, it is important to note that in manure-intensive regions - like Flanders or the Netherlands - not all manure can be put in the field because of the Nitrates Directive, limiting its use to 170 kg N per hectare per year to prevent soil and water contamination. Therefore, a lot of manure needs to be exported or processed. Alternatively, manure can be used as feedstock for an AD plant. However, it should be noted that the digestate is still recognised as animal manure (as long as at least one drop of manure is entering the AD plant), meaning that its use on fields is limited to 170 kg N/ha. Cattle manure and pig manure are already widely used as a feedstock for AD: pig manure is often being used as co-substrate in an industrial AD plant, while cattle manure is already being used on approximately 60 farms in 2024 as substrate for mono-digestion in Flanders. Furthermore, there are also examples of mono-digestion of pig manure, but this is more complicated due to the lower C/N ratio.

In Flanders, 124.9 million kg N and 27.6 million kg P₂O₅ were produced from animal manure in 2022 (Mestrapport 2023, VLM). Since most of the manure comes from cattle and pigs, this chapter will focus on producing this type of manure. In 2022, there were 5.4 million pigs and 1.25 million cattle in Flanders. Assuming an annual manure production of 30 tonnes for cattle and 1 tonne for pigs equals 37.5 million tonnes of cattle manure and 5.4 million tonnes of pig manure. Of this manure, almost all cattle manure is being used on the fields, while this is only 60% in the case of pig manure. The remaining 40% is being processed or exported. One main reason not all pig manure can be put on the fields is the P-limiting soils in Flanders.

⁸ <https://inagro.be/projecten/chicoryrepowered>

4. ANAEROBIC DIGESTION AND BIOMETHANE PRODUCTION

The Belgian demo will assess several aspects of biogas valorisation, focusing on efficient electricity and heat production via an innovative microturbine, and mobility solutions by powering a biogas tractor with biomethane obtained via in situ biomethanation. These systems are already briefly described in the report on demonstrations' specifications (D1.2) and will be reported more in detail in WP3 (Demonstration of the optimised value chains).

4.1. ANAEROBIC DIGESTION

AD is the process through which bacteria break down organic matter without oxygen. AD is a fully natural process that converts rich organic biomass into biogas and digestate. The process usually takes place in a Continuously Stirred Tank Reactor (CSTR) at mesophilic (35-45 °C) or thermophilic (50-60 °C) temperatures. The Dry Matter (DM) content in the CSTR is maximally 15%. Other systems with higher DM content also exist but are not discussed in this deliverable. All biomass containing organic matter will digest, but it is important to note that every biomass stream has its biogas potential - indicating how much biogas can be produced out of 1 m³ of biomass - and- ideally - the biomass should be available all year round in large quantities since AD is a continuously ongoing process. Since agricultural residues are widely available, they have the potential to be a good feedstock for AD.

The usual way of valorising biogas - mainly consisting out of methane - is by burning it in a Combined Heat and Power (CHP) unit to produce renewable heat and electricity (Figure 7). However, since the electrical efficiency of a CHP is only about 30%, it is important to also valorise the residual heat. This is not always the case on certain farms, increasing the need to look for alternative biogas valorisation. Therefore, the biogas can also be upgraded to biomethane, a process in which the project's feasibility, economics, and sustainability will be further investigated.

For farmers wanting to implement AD on their farms, INA has a lot of hands-on information available (in Dutch) on their website⁹ and in brochures¹⁰. Next, INA coordinates several Operational Groups (OGs) related to farm-scale AD, focusing on providing hands-on information and raising awareness¹¹.

⁹ <https://inagro.be/themas/energie/energie-produceren/pocketvergisting>

¹⁰ <https://inagro.be/sites/default/files/media/files/2022-04/BrochureKleinschaligeVergisting.pdf>

¹¹ <https://inagro.be/projecten/pocketboer-2>, <https://inagro.be/projecten/boost-pocketvergisting-en-nabewerking>

Figure 7: Anaerobic digestion of agricultural biomass: Left: biogas is being produced in a reactor. Right: the biogas is burned in a CHP to produce renewable heat and electricity

4.2. BIOMETHANE PRODUCTION

In Europe, there is a rapid increase in biomethane production, with a production of 44 TWh or 4.2 bcm in 2022, equalling a growth of almost 20% compared to the year before. By the end of 2022, Europe was home to 1,323 biomethane production facilities, of which 1,124 in EU-27 (EBA Statistical Report, 2023). As can be seen in Figure 8, several technologies to produce biomethane out of biogas already exist (Khan et al., 2021). However, biomethane production has only been implemented on large-scale AD plants, with an average capacity typically almost four times larger than biogas plants (33 GWh/year compared to 9 GWh/year). Therefore, it is not yet known what the most cost-effective and sustainable upgrading technology is at the farm level.

More than $\frac{3}{4}$ of the biomethane plants currently active use either membrane separation (51%), water scrubbing (14%) or chemical scrubbing (12%) as their upgrading technology. The remaining plants use pressure swing adsorption (10%), physical scrubbing (2%) and cryogenic separation (1%). For 10% of European biomethane plants, no data concerning the upgrading technology is available (EBA Statistical Report, 2023).

Figure 8: Biogas upgrading technologies (Khan et al., 2021)

The next paragraphs provide an overview of three possibilities, which will all be investigated more via the AD pilot plant of INA (Figure 7), and reported in detail as part of WP 3 (Demonstration of the optimised value chains).

4.2.1. Membrane separation

Membrane separation is by far the most used technology for biogas upgrading, with over 50% of the biomethane plants implementing this. The upgrading process is based on different molecules' particle size and chemical affinity. Treatment of biogas using membrane separation technology has recently been compared to other techniques and is relatively straightforward. Membrane separation does not have high operational requirements; the biggest drawback is the high initial investment cost. Impurities such as water vapour and hydrogen sulphide must be removed from raw biogas, which is then compressed to increase the pressure. This compressed gas is passed through a membrane separator that removes CO₂. The upgraded biogas leaves the membrane separator on the high-pressure side while the impurities are removed at the low-pressure side.

4.2.2. Pressure Swing Adsorption

About 10% of the European biomethane plants use Pressure Swing Adsorption (PSA) as their biogas upgrading technology. The basic principle of the upgrading process is that gas molecules are adsorbed on an adsorbent material based on their molecular sizes. Due to its larger size, CH₄ can be separated from CO₂. In this process, the raw biogas is compressed at 4-10 bars and introduced into the adsorption column that will adsorb the impurities such as H₂S, CO₂, H₂O, O₂ and N₂. The methane gas does not adsorb onto the adsorbent due to its larger molecular size, which is collected at the top of the adsorption column at low pressure. Generally, the process is made continuous by installing four adsorption columns together, as shown in Figure 9. Before the adsorbent material is completely saturated, biogas goes to another vessel already regenerated to achieve continuous operation. After the saturation of the adsorbent, the pressure is reduced, causing the adsorbed impurities to be removed and the adsorbing material to be regenerated.

Figure 9: Schematic overview of PSA (Khan et al., 2021)

4.2.3. In situ biomethanation

Via in situ biomethanation, hydrogen gas (H₂) is injected in the reactor. The injected gas is converted to CH₄ by methanogenic bacteria and CO₂, via the following reaction: $\text{CO}_2 + 4 \text{H}_2 \rightarrow \text{CH}_4 + 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Under optimal pH and temperature conditions, about 99% of potential methane can be recovered using this process. The main advantage of this technology is its rather low investment cost. Still, one of the main challenges is the limited mass transfer of H₂ in the bioreactor fluid, which results in much of the injected H₂ entering the headspace unchanged. Because of that, additional safety measures need to be taken into account. Therefore, this technology is still in the research phase.

4.3. BENEFITS OF BIOGAS AND BIOMETHANE

Once biogas and biomethane are produced, several valorisation pathways depend on their CH₄ content. Biogases can be pivotal in delivering Europe's long-term energy security and climate mitigation objectives as part of a forward-looking and balanced renewable energy mix. Besides, their benefits go far beyond the reduction of greenhouse emissions. To this end, the European Biogas Association (EBA) published six factsheets highlighting the multiple solutions biogases already provide in developing a European bioeconomy (EBA, 2023). These are summarised below and can be accessed in detail by clicking the Figures.

4.3.1. Energy system integration

Flexibility is paramount in enabling the transition to a power system dominated by renewables, which will include increasing quotas of variable sources providing fluctuating levels of electricity. Enabling and encouraging different energy sectors to work together optimises the function of the energy system as a whole. It is more effective than decarbonising and making separate efficiency gains in each sector. Biogas and biomethane can be produced at a relatively constant pace and then used to generate electricity as needed, making it possible to offer dynamic electricity production that can accommodate fluctuations in electricity demand. This promotes grid stability and provides additional options for seasonal energy storage.

Biogas and biomethane are important sources of flexibility in the energy system. They contribute to all energy outputs - electricity, heat and transport - and can support the further integration of variable renewables via three main pathways:

1. CHP systems
2. Biomethanation
3. Biomethane

4.3.2. Regenerative agriculture

Agriculture depends on weather, land, water and natural resources, making it particularly susceptible to climate change. Issues such as soil erosion and degradation, more frequent and more severe droughts, water pollution, and biodiversity losses pose a significant challenge. If the agricultural sector does not find ways to address these adverse conditions, it will increasingly lead to consumer price volatility and severely impact the affordability of food items.

Regenerative agriculture is vital to developing an adaptive, sustainable food system, reducing the use of water and other inputs, and preventing land degradation and deforestation. It positively impacts climate, soil health, resource use efficiency, biodiversity, and prosperity. The regenerative approach promotes agronomic practices such as adopting alternatives to synthetic fertilisers, reducing pesticide and/or tillage (preparation of the soil by mechanical agitation), and providing soil cover through cover crops, including sequential crops. These practices increase carbon sequestration potential, improve the health and fertility of the soil, facilitate the recycling of nutrients plants need for growth, enhance water retention capacity and help protect natural habitats.

Since regeneration is about increasing the positive impact on the environment, biogas systems provide multiple benefits in line with the principles of regenerative agriculture:

1. Using manure or agricultural residues as feedstocks for AD mitigates GHG emissions and nitrate leaching. Additionally, if we combine sequential cropping with biogas production, the second crop grown - a cover or catch crop with multiple environmental benefits - is often unsuitable for food or feed and can be better valorised through AD.
2. AD converts feedstocks into two valuable assets: renewable energy and digestate. When spread on fields, digestate is an organic fertiliser that improves soil health, allows carbon sequestration, and promotes plant disease resistance. The use of digestate also reduces GHG emissions by replacing the use of synthetic fertilisers.
3. Both the main crop harvest and livestock farming provide consumers with quality food.

4.3.3. Transport

The transport sector currently accounts for about a quarter of the EU's total greenhouse gas emissions, despite efficiency improvements and the emergence of climate mitigation policies. Almost three-quarters of the EU's transport emissions come from road transport.

Existing policy measures are expected to curb a thirty-year upward trend in Europe's transport emissions. However, without applying a technology-neutral approach, the reduction in emissions may not be enough to meet the EU's 2050 climate-neutrality target.

Biomethane provides a sustainable and cost-competitive substitute for fossil fuels, representing one of the few readily available fossil fuel alternatives for long-distance and energy-intensive transport segments. This makes biomethane a key player in transitioning to a climate-neutral economy.

4.3.4. Heating

Buildings are the single biggest consumers of energy in the EU, accounting for 42% of final energy consumption and 36% of CO₂ emissions. Only 23% of primary energy for buildings comes from renewable sources. The transition to a carbon-neutral building stock will require various tools, and biogases offer easy-to-implement and cost-effective solutions. Biogases can provide heat for residential and tertiary buildings, directly on-site or off-site with distribution via a district heating grid. A range of appliances can meet the on-site generation needs of different buildings, whether individual or collective, old or newly built. Mini-CHP (for collective buildings) and fuel cell units (for individual houses) generate heat and electricity. Other options can be combined with electric appliances to provide a highly efficient hybrid solution - for instance, a biomethane-fuelled boiler combined with an electric heat pump.

Biogases can provide households and tertiary buildings with renewable, cost-competitive heat in the following ways:

1. Once injected into gas grids, biomethane (i.e. biogas upgraded to natural gas quality), can fuel end-use appliances such as highly efficient gas boilers and gas or hybrid heat pumps, both in individual and in collective buildings.
2. Central CHP units can be run on biomethane and provide heat through a district heating network.

3. In rural areas not connected to existing gas networks, raw biogas can directly generate heat to be distributed through a district heating network.

4.3.5. Industrial uses

The industry was responsible for over a quarter of the EU's final energy consumption in 2021. However, less than 10% of that year's industrial energy demand was met using renewable sources. Natural gas, in contrast, accounts for 33% of the energy use in the industrial sector.

The transition to a low-carbon industry in Europe will require various tools because of the diversity of the processes involved. Energy needs vary tremendously. Gas can be used to generate process heat or to provide methane for use as a feedstock. Biogas can meet the needs of many processes, especially those requiring high temperatures and steam pressure. In 2022, the industry used 18% of upgraded biogas, which is set to increase.

Biogas can help to decarbonise industrial processes in the following ways:

1. Biomethane can directly replace natural gas for both energy and feedstock purposes because biomethane is just like natural gas: it is chemically equivalent and contains the same amount of energy.
2. BioLPG can replace fossil LPG using the same delivery method (trucks refilling on-site tanks).
3. Raw biogas or biomethane can produce renewable electricity, heat and steam on-site via CHP generators.
4. Biomethane can be easily sourced using the existing gas networks. It is fully compatible with existing gas infrastructure and end-use appliances (boilers, furnaces, etc.), meaning there is no adaptation cost for industries already using natural gas.

Additionally, biogenic CO₂ can be used in several ways by industry, and its demand is expected to grow significantly over the next years.

4.3.6. Sustainability

Sustainability ensures our well-being while respecting our environment and that of future generations: it underpins the further development of biogases in Europe. The production and use of biogas in the EU must comply with a set of sustainability criteria that came into force in 2018. These criteria ensure that sourcing feedstock does not negatively impact biodiversity and the environment, biogases are used efficiently, and GHG emissions are substantially reduced relative to the use of fossil fuels. Over the past decade, significant steps have been taken to preserve our natural environment. The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development outlines 17 sustainable development goals (SDGs) linked to three main pillars (environment, society, and economy); the achievement of many of these can be supported via the production and use of biogas.

4.4. BIOMETHANE POTENTIAL

4.4.1. Europe

The EBA and Gas Infrastructure Europe (GIE) published a biomethane map, showcasing the most recent and available data on Europe's biomethane plants. This map can be accessed via the EBA website.¹² Europe reached a total of 1,322 biomethane-producing facilities by April 2023. France and Germany have the most biomethane plants.

However, since the European Commission set a target of 35 bcm of annual biomethane production by 2030 in its recent REPowerEU plan, a further increase in biomethane production is necessary. Today, 3 bcm of biomethane and 15 bcm of biogas are produced in the EU-27, but it is estimated that enough sustainable feedstocks are available to produce up to 41 bcm of biomethane in 2030 and 151 bcm in 2050 (Alberici et al., 2022).

4.4.2. Belgium

According to Gas.be (2019), the realistic biomethane potential in Belgium is 15.6 TWh - representing a GHG emission reduction of 6 million tonnes CO_{2,eq} per year - of which 46.5% is located in Flanders and 53% in Wallonia. Of the 15.6 TWh of potential, 80% has a link with agriculture: animal manure accounts for 29% of the total potential (4439 GWh), crops (intermediate cropping, grassland, energy crops) for 37% (5730 GWh) and crop residues for 14% (2140 GWh). Most of the potential is located in the Hesbaya region because of crop residues and intermediate cropping potential, as well as in regions with a lot of animal husbandry, such as the province of West Flanders. The positive aspects of biomethane

¹² https://www.europeanbiogas.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/GIE_EBA_Biomethane-Map-2022-2023.pdf

are multiple: next to energy generation, positive externalities can be found in energy and waste, agricultural practices and economic activities (Gas.be, 2019).

Figure 10: Biomethane potential in Belgium (Gas.be, 2019)

More specifically, in Flanders, only 14% of the biogas potential is being valorised (Tessens & Vergote, 2021). To increase the biomethane production in Flanders, a roadmap was published (Tessens, 2022) on how to realise the production potential in a cost-effective and sustainable way, consisting out of three phases ranked according to their abatement cost (cost per ton CO₂ avoided):

- First phase: manure digestion - AD of 100% fresh manure has the lowest abatement cost of 58-5 EUR per ton CO₂ avoided. Ideally, the capacity is between 100,000 and 300,000 tonnes of manure per year and should be as fresh as possible.
- Second phase: co-digestion of manure and agroresidues (excluding energy crops), which has an abatement cost of 419-62 EUR per ton CO₂ avoided. The economies of scale is important here. Ideally, the capacity should be around 400,000 tonnes per year.
- Third phase: AD of intermediate crops and energy crops, but this has the highest abatement cost (more than 500 EUR per ton CO₂ avoided)

A scenario analysis revealed that almost all potential can be reached for a cost of less than 55 EUR per ton CO₂ avoided (when the RENURE criteria¹³ are implemented in legislation). This would have a CO₂ reduction of 1.8 Mton CO₂ (or 2.44% of the CO_{2,eq} emissions in Flanders in 2019) and an estimated investment cost of 91 million EUR. When valorising the whole potential, including energy crops, this would have a CO₂ reduction of 1.98 Mton (or 2.61% of total CO_{2,eq} emissions in Flanders) and an investment cost of 163 million EUR. Given the high abatement cost for AD of intermediate and energy crops, this deliverable will not assess this further in detail.

¹³ “RENURE”: any nitrogen containing substance fully or partially derived from livestock manure through processing under controlled conditions that can be used in areas with water pollution by nitrogen following the same provisions applied to nitrogen containing chemical fertilisers as defined in the Nitrates Directive (91/676/EEC), while providing adequate agronomic benefits to enhance plant growth.

5. LOCAL ANALYSIS OF AVAILABLE BIOMASS SUITABLE FOR ANAEROBIC DIGESTION

As already discussed in Chapter 3 - Local analysis of available biomass in Flanders, there are quite some potential interesting residual biomass streams to feed to an AD plant. This is also confirmed in Figure 11, showing the huge remaining potential for biogas production out of crop residues and manure in Flanders (Tessens & Vergote, 2021). Manure has the highest potential to produce more biogas, followed by agricultural crop residues, such as the ones discussed in Chapter 3 (leek residues, chicory residues, horticultural crop residues). Co-digestion of manure and crop residues has a lot of potential as well. A similar trend is shown in Figure 12, emphasising that 39% of the European AD feedstock mix in 2040 can consist out of agricultural residues and animal manure, and another 43% out of sequential crops (Guidehouse, 2024). Since Flanders is a nutrient intensive region with a lot of animal husbandry, it is a logical consequence that the potential of manure is higher than the average in Europe.

The next paragraphs will dive deep into the potential of each side stream, which will support different stakeholders in providing the best possible advice and trade-offs for handling each residual stream. Each sub-chapter provides some information on how the residual streams come available during the harvest of these crops, the biogas potential, a short comparison between biogas production and the business as usual and the recycling of nutrients. As a kind of summary, a SWOT analysis for introducing AD on these agroresidues was performed based on communication with several experts from research and outcomes of the Focus Group discussions in Work Package 1.

Figure 11: Current and potential energy production out of biogas in Flanders (derived from Tessens & Vergote, 2021)

Figure 12: 2040 AD feedstock mix in Europe (Guidehouse, 2024)

5.1. (HYDRO)LEEK RESIDUES

5.1.1. Harvest

The plants are cut off during the harvest, leaving the roots unharvested and on the field. Leeks grown for the fresh market are then brought to a washing installation, where the top leaves are separated from the leek. Therefore, these top leaves are quite easy to collect. Leeks grown for industry are cut on the field, causing a bigger challenge to collect residual biomass streams during harvest.

For the cultivation of hydroleeks, a robot harvester was designed which offers a big logistical advantage compared to leeks cultivated on the field. The top leaves and roots are collected separately during the cutting process, providing two separate residual biomass streams. Another big advantage is that there is no contamination with inorganic matter, like soil residues, because of its cultivation on water.

5.1.2. Biogas potential

According to Tessens (2022), the biogas potential of leeks is 115 Nm³/tonne. However, it is not specified if this potential is for the full plant or crop residues only. The Flemish Vlaio LA-project Pocket Power

looked into leek residues' potential for use in a biogas plant. Biogas potential tests revealed a methane potential of 21 - 30 m³ CH₄/tonne. Assuming a methane content of 55% in the biogas, the biogas potential is 38 - 55 m³/tonne. This varying biogas potential can be due to the samples' freshness and inorganic material's presence (Vandendriessche et al., 2020).

Since there is no data on the biogas potential of hydroleek yet, INA took samples of crop residues that could potentially be interesting for AD to be analysed for its biogas potential. The results for the roots and top leaves are shown in **Fout! Verwijzingsbron niet gevonden..**

Table 3 : Biogas potential of the residual crop streams of hydroleeks (roots and top leaves)

	Roots	Top leaves
Dry matter (%)	3.84	10.39
Organic dry matter (%)	72.42	89.47
Raw fat (kg/tonne)	0.436	3.69
Raw protein (kg/tonne)	6.20	21.5
Carbohydrates (kg/tonne)	13.1	42.4
Biogas potential (m ³ biogas/tonne)	14 ± 1	50 ± 3
Methane content (%)	57	58
Methane potential (m ³ CH ₄ /tonne)	8 ± 0	29 ± 1

As seen from the Table above, the top leaves have a similar potential as found in Pocket Power (50 ± 3 m³ biogas / tonne). Hence, it could be a potentially interesting biomass stream for farm-scale AD. Although the biogas potential expressed per tonne organic matter (OM) is similar for the roots (503.43 m³ biogas / tonne OM) compared to the top leaves (537.87 m³ biogas / tonne), the roots seem to be less interesting because of their lower DM content and consequently their lower biogas potential (14 ± 1 m³ biogas / tonne).

5.1.3. Biogas compared to business as usual

Nowadays, leek residues are usually brought back into the field to provide some organic nitrogen bound to the soil. Attention should be paid to the risk of diseases, so it is not recommended to bring it back to fields where there will be another cultivation of leeks (T. De Cuyper, personal communication, 28 March, 2024). Bringing these residues back to the field could cause some odour nuisance and does not generate an added value for the grower. Some research has already been done to valorise these

residual biomass streams in an alternative way, but up to date, no economically viable alternative has been found:

- The green part of leek contains many health-promoting components (such as polyphenols and vitamins). However, due to its strong colour and pungent flavour, it is not an easy product to further process in food.
- Bernaert et al. (2022) used leek powder as an additive for bakery products. Although the drying method has a big impact on the quality of the powder, it could be noted that 1 g leek powder per 100 g flour is an acceptable additive. However, the drying is quite expensive, making it difficult to be a profitable business case.
- Leek extract has the potential as an ingredient to stabilise emulsions. Stable emulsions can be obtained by homogenising leek extract at high pressure (e.g. 1000 bar) and achieving an acid pH. The emulsions were stable at 4°C for a period of at least 3 months. At higher storage temperatures (20-35°C), the emulsions were stable for 1 month. The emulsion stabilising ability of the leek extract is probably not primarily related to pectin but to the protein fraction (most probably RuBisCo) in this extract. This protein fraction is presumably also responsible for the gelling ability of the leek extract (No Waste Project, 2015).

In general, quite some examples of alternative valorisation of top leaves have been examined, but there is lack of interest for large-scale production. The roots are a new, potentially interesting product with a unique structure and flavour, but there is no experience yet with this residual biomass stream.

As an alternative, leek residues can be valorised in a farm-scale AD plant. Assuming a methane potential of 30 m³ CH₄/tonne and a yearly biomass production of 750 tonnes top leaves and peeling residues (5 ha * 150 tonnes/ha), there is a yearly CH₄ production of 22,500 m³ CH₄. Since the energy content of 1 m³ CH₄ is about 10 kWh, this equals a total electric yield of 225,000 kWh. Since an average CHP has an electric efficiency of about 32% and a thermal efficiency of about 55%, this equals a gross 72,000 kWh of available electric energy and 123,750 kWh of available heat. Additionally, extra biogas can be produced out of the roots, but this is not taken into account since the biogas potential of the roots is rather low. The business case can be calculated depending on the investment cost, subsidies and operational support, the amount of electricity and heat that can be consumed on farm, and the energy price.

5.1.4. Recycling of nutrients

The top leaves and roots from a hydroleeks production facility, having an estimated production of 100 tonnes/ha and 75 tonnes/ha respectively, have the following composition (Veiling, 2022).

Table 4: Nutrient composition of hydroleeks residues

	Roots	Top leaves
Dry matter (%)	3.70 - 4.94	8.1 - 10.0
Ca (g/kg)	0.48 - 0.41	0.39 - 0.64
Mg (g/kg)	0.07 - 0.12	0.11 - 0.16
K (g/kg)	3.71 - 5.71	3.45 - 4.47
Na (g/kg)	0.08 - 0.14	0.02 - 0.04
Cl (mg/kg)	63 - 127	524 - 1053
P (g/kg)	0.45 - 1.02	0.41 - 3.8
N _{tot} (g/kg)	1.5 - 2.5	2.8 - 3.8

No analysis of the nutrients after AD is available. Still, in general, the process of AD does not impact the total amount of nutrients, except for carbon, so it can be recycled in the digestate when used as a fertiliser.

5.1.5. SWOT analysis

Table 5: SWOT analysis of using leek residues as substrate for AD production

Strengths	Weaknesses
Availability throughout the year; Good biogas potential for the top leaves	Rather low biogas potential of the roots; Extra work might be required to collect the residual streams (especially in the case of field leek)
Opportunities	Threats
The valorisation of crop residues could generate an extra income; Hydroleek residues are free of inorganic material; Top leaves could be a potentially interesting substrate for co-digestion with manure; The digestate can be used as a fertiliser again	No installations in practice yet; Extra pretreatment steps might be needed for the residual biomass streams (cleaning, shredding)

5.2. HORTICULTURAL RESIDUE STREAMS

5.2.1. Harvest

During the cultivation of horticultural vegetables (such as tomatoes, cucumbers, and bell peppers), there is an almost continuous stream of biomass residues from leaves during the growing period. Removing these leaves is necessary for the growth of the fruit and vegetables. At the end of each growing period, the greenhouses are being cleaned, providing a bulk stream of stems and leaves potentially contaminated with plastic and metal clips.

5.2.2. Biogas potential

According to Tessens (2022), the biogas potential of these vegetables is about 60 Nm³ biogas/tonne. In literature, some papers discussed the potential to use these residual streams for AD, but mostly as co-substrate. It could be concluded that cucumber waste co-digestion with sewage sludge is effective, although numerous conditions could be utilised to optimise gas production (Lowe et al., 2020). According to Gioulounta et al. (2023), the biomethane potential of suckers, leaves and stalks of tomato and cucumber waste yielded a range of 221-357, 210-296, and 225-250 Nm³ / tonne volatile solids (VS), respectively. It was also revealed that the biochemical methane potential (BMP) of the leaves and suckers were statistically different for tomato and cucumber plants. The BMP of stalks was lower than the other residue types except for the tomato leaves. Despite having a higher BMP than the stalks, leaves and suckers exhibit a lower maximum specific methane production rate constant than the stalks during the first phase, which may indicate the presence of inhibitory or slowly biodegradable compounds in leaves and suckers in comparison to the stalks.

Table 6 shows the biogas potential of cucumber and tomato leaves taken by INA at 11 March, 2024.

Table 6: Biogas potential of horticultural biomass residues

	Cucumber leaves	Tomato leaves
Dry matter (%)	7.88	10.02
Organic dry matter (%)	72.83	77.81
Raw fat (kg/ton)	1.11	1.73
Raw protein (kg/ton)	20.4	20.3
Carbohydrates (kg/ton)	16.3	28.7
Biogas potential (m³ biogas/ton)	27 ± 1	37 ± 2
Methane content (%)	61	59
Methane potential (m³ CH₄/ton)	16 ± 1	22 ± 1

It can be seen that the biogas potential of the cucumber leaves is lower than the tomato leaves. However, the biogas potential per tonne OM is quite similar (470.46 Nm³ biogas/tonne OM for cucumber leaves and 474.57 Nm³ biogas/tonne OM for tomato leaves). These values are also lower than the ones mentioned by Tessens (2022), but it should be noted that the type of biomass was not specified in that report.

Szilágyi et al. (2021) mentioned that tomato waste might have an inhibitory effect on the microbial community. Tomato plant materials contain e.g. flavonoids, glycoalkaloids (such as tomatine and tomatidine), etc. known as antimicrobial and antifungal agents. The negative effect of tomatine on the biogas yield was confirmed in batch fermentation experiments. Metagenomic analysis revealed that the tomato plant waste caused significant rearrangements in the microbial communities in the continuously operated reactors. The results demonstrated that tomato waste could be a good mono-substrate in batch fermentations or a co-substrate with corn stover in a proper ratio in continuous anaerobic biogas production. These results also point to the importance of running long-term continuous fermentations to test the suitability of a novel biomass substrate for industrial biogas production.

When addressing these concerns, both tomato waste and cucumber waste seem to have potential for AD. Since bell peppers have only one growing cycle per year and the continuous biomass stream of leaves is lower than for the other vegetables, this crop is not assessed further in detail.

5.2.3. Biogas compared to business as usual

The almost continuous available biomass stream of leaves is mostly being composted nowadays. The bulk stream, which is available at the end of each harvest, is being processed since it mostly contains metal or plastic clips and strings. This is a huge cost for a horticultural farmer, going up to 150-196 EUR/tonne. Hence, valorising these residual biomass streams via AD could be potentially interesting. However, it should be noted that contaminants (such as metal or plastic clips) can have a negative impact. This waste stream should be avoided as much as possible. Biobased materials could offer a solution, but are often not cost effective.

5.2.4. Recycling of nutrients

In horticulture, only synthetic fertilisers are being used. However, since in certain systems, there is a closed nutrient loop where nutrients are continuously recirculated, recycled nutrients can be used because there is no risk for leaching. Therefore, introducing biobased fertilisers in conventional horticulture could also be interesting, such as the liquid fraction of digestate. This feasibility is being explored within the Flemish project Hermest, where biobased fertilisers are being tested in closed cropping systems such as chicory, strawberries and lettuce.

5.2.5. SWOT analysis

Table 7: SWOT analysis of using horticultural residues as substrate for AD production

Strengths	Weaknesses
Almost continuous biomass stream (leaves)	Contaminants in the bulk biomass stream (plastic clips, metal rings)
Opportunities	Threats
Cost reduction for the grower; Closing nutrients and energy cycles; Biodegradable clips and strings can offer a solution for the plastic and metal in the bulk stream	Plant pathogens may cause the demolition of crops which might cause a shortage as biogas feed; Logistic aspects (leaves are being processed decentral, while the bulk waste stream is mostly being processed central by a waste processor); Tomato waste (and potentially other vegetable waste streams) might contain antimicrobial agents, lowering the biogas yield

5.3. CHICORY RESIDUES

5.3.1. Harvest

The cultivation of chicory consists of two parts: the cultivation of the roots and then the forcing of the roots, thus the cultivation of the crops. The result of the forcing strongly depends on the quality of the root. Many chicory growers, therefore, grow their roots on their own farms or leased plots. However, some entrepreneurs have their roots grown under contract and only do the forcing. The forcing can take place in pits covered with soil or other material or in stacked forcing bins with flowing water, which is up to date the most important way of cultivating chicory.

5.3.2. Biogas potential

Tessens (2018) revealed that chicory roots can potentially produce 700,000 Nm³ biomethane in Flanders. In the Operational Group ChicoryRePowered framework, INA took samples of both chicory leaves and chicory roots to assess their biogas potential (Table 8).

Table 8: Biogas potential of chicory residues

	Chicory leaves	Chicory roots
Dry matter (%)	4.08	14.60
Organic dry matter (%)	87.99	67.10
Raw fat (kg/ton)	0.337	2.02
Raw protein (kg/ton)	4.79	6.49
Carbohydrates (kg/ton)	25.9	79.6
Biogas potential (m ³ biogas/ton)	23 ± 1	66 ± 3
Methane content (%)	53	52
Methane potential (m ³ CH ₄ /ton)	12 ± 1	34 ± 2

This shows a big difference in the biogas potential of leaves (23 m³/tonne) on the one hand and roots (66 m³/tonne) on the other. The higher OM content of roots can explain this. The methane content is similar for both samples. The roots show a sufficiently high biogas potential at first sight, but considering the high DM content, another liquid stream (such as manure or leaves) should be added. Since growers indicate that it is advantageous to valorise as many leaves as possible, five BioMethane Potential (BMP) tests were conducted with different ratios of roots and leaves, allowing the biogas production over time to be monitored for all ratios (Table 9). During the tests, a certain quantity of substrate was added to anaerobic sludge in the mesophilic temperature range (38 °C). A negative control was added to quantify the gas production of the inoculum.

These tested ratios were the following:

1. 50% roots and 50% leaves
2. 60% roots and 40% leaves
3. 70% roots and 30% leaves
4. 80% roots and 20% leaves
5. 90% roots and 10% leaves

Table 9: BMP tests of different ratios of chicory leaves and roots

	50/50	60/40	70/30	80/20	90/10
Dry Matter (%)	10,46	11,72	12,41	12,96	13,50
Organic Dry Matter (%)	76,29	74,67	75,50	76,72	77,14
Organic Matter (%)	7,98	8,75	9,37	9,94	10,41
pH	5,44	5,39	5,35	5,29	5,31
Biogas production (Nm³/ton)	46,8	42,6	50,9	54,3	54,1
Biogas production (Nm³/ton ODM)	586,5	486,8	543,2	546,1	519,5
Methane content (%)	60,3	61,8	60,5	60,4	62,0
CO₂ content (%)	39,7	38,2	39,5	39,6	38,0
H₂S content (ppm)	80	61	152	168	233
Methane production (Nm³/ton)	28,2	26,3	30,8	32,8	33,5
Methane production (Nm³/ton ODM)	353,6	300,8	328,7	329,9	322,1

In general, it could be noted that all ratios show a similar constant increase over time, reaching 90% of the total biogas production after 30-33 days, with no further increase after 39-43 days. In other words, a hydraulic retention time (HRT) of 30 to 40 days is advisable. Since roots have a higher DM content than leaves (Table 8), the DM content logically increases as more roots are fed into the digester. A similar trend is observed when considering the OM content. Considering the initial results (Table 8), it can be expected that the biogas potential increases when more roots are fed to the digester. Since the methane content is similar for all ratios (fluctuating between 60.3% and 62.0%), a similar trend is expected for the methane potential. However, surprisingly, this test revealed that the 50/50 ratio had a higher biogas yield (and consequently methane yield) than the 60/40 ratio, despite using the same batch of roots and leaves for this test. Compared to the 60/40 ratio, the 90/10 ratio yields about 21% extra biogas production (42.6 m³ biogas/ton vs. 54.1 m³ biogas/ton).

The H₂S content increases as more roots are fed into the digester. However, the H₂S content of all ratios is considered average, meaning there is no indication of process inhibition due to the sulphur content.

5.3.3. Biogas compared to business as usual

Generally, chicory farms have a high energy demand due to cooling infrastructure. Therefore, producing biogas with their own waste streams could be interesting. To date, many chicory roots are being valorised as fodder, for which farmers receive 3-10 EUR per tonne. The leaves are not yet valorised and pose a significant cost to get rid of them. Therefore, growers are especially interested in the potential to apply AD on chicory leaves. However, it is difficult to make this economically feasible due to the low biogas potential of chicory leaves.

Additionally, a lot of digestate will be produced because of the low DM content. Nevertheless, as seen in Table 9, a ratio of roots and leaves can be potentially interesting. Logically, the more roots are being fed

to the AD plant, the more biogas is being produced. Therefore, an economic analysis must consider whether reduced biogas production (due to feeding more leaves) is financially viable.

5.3.4. Recycling of nutrients

The feasibility of using biobased fertilisers for chicory cultivation is being investigated within the Flemish project Hermest. However, it should be noted that in general, chicory farms do not have a big need for fertilisation.

5.3.5. SWOT analysis

Table 10 : SWOT analysis of using chicory residues as substrate for AD production

Strengths	Weaknesses
<p>The combination of leaves and roots could be a good substrate for AD production;</p> <p>Chicory roots have a comparable biogas potential compared to other biomass streams used for AD</p>	<p>Rather low biogas potential of the leaves, because of the low DM content</p>
Opportunities	Threats
<p>Potential valorisation of the leaves;</p> <p>Generally, chicory farms have a high energy demand</p>	<p>Competition with fodder as valorisation for the roots</p>

5.4. MANURE

5.4.1. Storage

In classic stables, the manure is collected in a pit emptied once in several weeks, causing GHG and NH₃ emissions. This classic stable system is incompatible with AD since manure needs to be fed as fresh as possible to an AD plant to maximise the energy output. So, when using manure as feedstock, it is necessary to have an adapted stable system that provides fresh manure daily. Such systems already exist for cattle as well as pigs. However, it should be noted that collecting fresh manure daily is easier on dairy farms than on pig farms.

Cattle manure

The removal of daily fresh manure is already done quite often on dairy farms. Instead of having a slatted floor, the floor consists of full concrete with a manure scraper removing the manure a couple of times a day. Alternatively, the floor can consist of a kind of rubber mat with manure robots removing the manure (Figure 13).

Figure 13: Manure robot providing daily fresh manure on a cattle farm to feed an AD plant

Pig manure

Achieving daily fresh manure out of pig stables is more difficult than cattle stable systems. A literature review was done in the framework of the Flemish project Pocket Power to assess the possibilities. Vandendriessche et al. (2020) revealed that most current pig stable systems are not yet equipped to be compatible with an on-farm AD plant in the most cost-effective way, as the vast majority of pigs are housed in a traditional stable type with slurry being stored in the manure cellar. Recent developments towards low-emission stable constructions (e.g. acidification, daily manure removal, additives, ...) could increase the compatibility with an on-farm AD plant. However, this is particularly interesting for newly built stables, but difficult to achieve in already existing ones.

One example of such an operational system is the Vermeulen Dobbelaere Welfare System (VeDoWS). In such an adapted stable construction, pig manure is primarily separated into solid manure and urine. The separation occurs using a partly slatted floor system. Underneath the slatted floor, a shallow cellar is constructed, where the primary separation of urine and solid manure occurs. The cellar consists of two inclining parts with an 18 to 22 mm opening in the centre (Figure 14). Using a scraper, the solid manure is removed from the cellar multiple times a day. The pig urine trickles down to a separate collection channel through the scraping action.

Figure 14: Working principle of a VeDoWS stable system (© Beton Dobbelaere)

According to Georgitzikis et al. (2017), the main source of NH_3 is the rapid hydrolysis of urea by urease, leading to NH_4^+ . Primary separation of manure in the cellar can thus lead to lower NH_3 emissions due to minimal contact time between the pig urine and urease, which is present in the solid manure.

In the VeDoWS stable system, the average value for NH_3 and CH_4 emissions is 1.2 kg/animal place/year and 0.8 kg/animal place/year, respectively. The odour was estimated to be around 7.8 odour units/animal place/s, while this value is 29.2 odour units/animal place/s in normal circumstances (G. Vermeulen, personal communication, 2019). Furthermore, the resulting products each have their own benefits: the solid manure has a better biogas potential than raw pig manure, and the urine is better suited as a fertiliser because it contains most nitrogen and potassium and is not phosphorus limited. Due to the liquid composition of the pig urine, field application and dose is easy to set.

5.4.2. Biogas potential

As already mentioned earlier, manure is losing its biogas potential very quickly when it is simply stored. This can be seen in Figure 15, showing the rapid decrease in biogas potential of pig manure when it is simply stored without further processing steps. Therefore, using the manure as fresh as possible is very important.

Figure 15: Biogas potential of pig manure in function of the storage time

For cattle, a value of 58 m³ biogas/tonne is expected, while this is 32 m³ biogas/tonne for pig manure. However, it should be noted that primary separation is beneficial for AD since the thick fraction contains most of the organic matter that is readily available for AD. Therefore, the solid fraction of a VeDoWS stable system has a biogas potential of 110 m³ biogas/tonne, more than three times as high as pig manure. Nevertheless, it should be noted that the DM content of this VeDoWS manure is somewhat too high, and a more liquid stream should be added to prevent operational problems.

5.4.3. Biogas compared to business as usual

Manure is often used in the field as basic fertilisation. However, it should be noted that in nutrient-intensive regions like Flanders or the Netherlands, the amount of available manure exceeds the amount that can be put in the fields according to the limits of the Nitrate Directive (170 kg N /ha). Therefore, manure needs to be processed.

On dairy farms, implementing a farm-scale AD plant is already quite common, with over 60 installations in Flanders only. Mono digestion of pig manure is not yet common. Although there are also already two examples of where pig manure is being digested in a farm-scale AD plant, the remaining potential remains high with about 62% of the Flemish pig farms showing potential to implement farm-scale AD, assuming an HRT of 30 days and 100% self-consumption of the produced electricity (Vergote, 2020).

5.4.4. Recycling of nutrients

After AD of manure, it can be seen that the digestate contains about 30% less DM content. The total amount of nutrients (NPK) remains unchanged, but it will be more mineralised, making this a good

fertiliser because of the short-term and long-term availability of N. Also, the OM content decreases with about 30%, but the remaining Organic Carbon is stable, enriching soils with OM. It is important to highlight that the digestate is considered animal manure as soon as one drop of manure enters the AD plant, so it should be applied according to the limits set by the Nitrates Directive.

5.4.5. SWOT analysis

Table 11: SWOT analysis of using manure as substrate for AD production

Strengths	Weaknesses
Continuous availability; Easy to incorporate in new stables Already applied in practice	Less suitable for existing stables; Solid fraction requires an adapted AD system or co-digestion with a more liquid stream
Opportunities	Threats
Almost no mono-digestion on pig farms, so there is a huge remaining potential; The digestate is a good fertiliser, providing more mineralised nitrogen	Difficult to obtain permits in nutrient intensive regions

5.5. CO-DIGESTION OF MANURE AND CROP RESIDUES

The co-digestion of manure and crop residues presents a promising approach in sustainable waste management and renewable energy production. The interesting part of co-digestion is that the C/N ratio can be steered to an optimal value, maximising the energy output of the AD plant. Additionally, the fibrous nature of crop residues enhances the porosity of the digestion substrate, facilitating better mass transfer and gas exchange. One potential interesting example of co-digestion is VeDoWS manure and chicory leaves. The biogas potential of chicory leaves is rather low. Still, due to its low DM content, it could be a great co-substrate for VeDoWS manure, valorising the leaves via energy production.

Table 12: SWOT analysis of using manure and other agricultural residues as substrate for co-digestion

Strengths	Weaknesses
Continuous availability C/N ratio and DM content can be steered	Not ideal for decentralised AD plants, since a farmer will not continuously produce several co streams
Opportunities	Threats
Valorisation of agroresidues that are difficult substrates for mono-digestion	All digestate is considered as animal based

6. GUIDELINES FOR FARMERS WANTING TO INVEST IN ANAEROBIC DIGESTION

For farmers with an excess of agroresidues that are currently not valorised, it can be interesting to look into the valorisation of these agroresidues via AD. However, a profitable business case will not always be feasible. Therefore, a decision tree can help farmers by giving them some first insights in AD of their agroresidues, which will be integrated into the Open Online Course (OOC) as part of Work Package 4 (Assessment and optimisation of the value chain). The following paragraphs can already provide some meaningful insights for farmers to know if it could be interesting to check the practical and economical feasibility of AD in more detail.

6.1. WHEN IS ANAEROBIC DIGESTION INTERESTING FOR MY FARM?

AD can be a profitable business case on your farm when certain criteria are met. However, it should be noted that profitability is very farm-specific and should be approached more in detail, taking farm-specific data into account. Biomethane production and biogas as a renewable fuel for mobility are not described since there is no knowledge yet on how to best integrate this on the small-scale farm level. Information on this will become available later throughout the Value4Farm project.

The next paragraphs give an overview of important criteria for profiting from farm scale AD.

6.1.1. Which agroresidues are available?

To check the feasibility of a biogas project, it is important to correctly estimate the amount of available biomass streams for AD on your farm. In theory, all organic streams, both animal and crop-based, can be used as substrate for AD. However, it is important to note that there are some specific legislative aspects related to input of an AD plant, which may vary throughout several countries. The amount of agroresidues and their biogas potential are two very important parameters defining the return on investment (ROI), so it is important to know this. For instance, if you have cows or pigs, the available manure can be estimated based on the number of animals on your farm. As a guideline, you can use 1 tonne manure/year per fattening pig and up to 30 tonnes manure/year per dairy cow. However, it should be noted that this can vary depending on the feed and milk production.

Some organic waste streams are not released evenly throughout the year. Their volumes are typically linked to the seasons (e.g. some crop residues, grass clippings...). However, a biogas plant will perform best when the same streams are fed to the AD plant in equal volumes throughout the year because the microbial community in the biogas reactor is adapted to a certain 'diet'. It is important to keep several operational parameters as constant as possible (such as temperature, dry matter, organic matter, C/N ratio, FOS/TAC ratio, ...) to provide the best conditions for the microorganisms to produce biogas out of the agroresidues. For streams that are released periodically, it is therefore important to stock them, so

that they can be fed into the biogas plant evenly throughout the year. Note that most organic streams spontaneously lose biogas potential as a result of the natural putrefaction process. Investing in a proper, adapted storage tank might, therefore, be important.

6.1.2. Are the available residues suitable for anaerobic digestion?

In practice, not all biomass streams are equally interesting for AD. In some cases, pre-mixing or diminishing the biomass might be necessary to increase biogas production. Unwanted components, such as plastic or metal, must be removed because they can cause operational problems. Consequently, a solution must be found for the metal and plastic clips and strings used in horticulture.

The chemical characteristics determine the digestibility of the biomass stream. For instance, plant material with a high crude fibre content is more difficult to digest. Streams rich in nitrogen (N), such as pig slurry, are also more difficult to ferment because a high N content in the biogas reactor can inhibit microbial activity. In that case, it might be better to look into co-digestion possibilities. For instance, co-digestion of pig manure and crop residues is something already done quite often on a large scale.

If you doubt whether your agroresidues have a good biogas potential or if there are no examples of AD of your agroresidue or co-digestion with another biomass stream, carrying out BMP tests before investing is highly recommended. These tests will inform you how much biogas you can get from a specific type of biomass, expressed in m³ biogas/tonne, which is a very important starting point for calculating the ROI.

6.1.3. How much green electricity can you produce?

How much biogas a certain agroresidue ultimately yields depends on the energetic value and digestibility of the biomass. The biogas you can produce from a biomass flow (*i.e.* at optimal Hydraulic Retention Time (HRT) in the biogas reactor) is called the biogas potential and is expressed in m³ biogas per tonne of biomass. For example, high-fat products have larger biogas potential than vegetable waste or manure. Average values for the biogas potential of several agroresidues are mentioned in Chapter 5 Local analysis of available biomass suitable for anaerobic digestion.

With this value and the methane content of the biogas, it is possible to calculate the annual amount of green electricity from the estimated amount of biogas per year, since one m³ of methane has an energy content of about 10 kWh. The annual green electricity production (1) can now be calculated using the formula below.

$$\begin{aligned} & (1) \text{ Green electricity production } \left(\frac{\text{kWh}}{\text{year}} \right) \\ & = \text{Total amount of biomass } \left(\frac{\text{tonnes}}{\text{year}} \right) \times \text{biogas potential } \left(\frac{\text{m}^3 \text{ biogas}}{\text{tonne}} \right) \\ & \times \text{methane content } (\%) \times 10 \frac{\text{kWh}}{\text{m}^3 \text{ CH}_4} \times \text{electric efficiency of the CHP}^{14} \end{aligned}$$

Next to this, renewable heat is being produced as well. As a thumb rule, one m³ of biogas produces 1,5-2 kWh electricity and 2-3 kWh heat. The required electrical power of the installation (2) is dependent on the amount of agroresidues available. This can be calculated by dividing the annual green electricity production by the yearly number of active hours of the biogas installation. Since it is sometimes necessary to temporarily shut down the installation for maintenance, it is recommended to consider a value of 7000 hours per year (instead of 8760 hours).

$$(2) \text{Electrical power of the biogas installation (kWel)} = \frac{\text{Green electricity production } \left(\frac{\text{kWh}}{\text{year}} \right)}{\text{running hours } \left(7000 \frac{\text{hours}}{\text{year}} \right)}$$

6.1.4. What is the investment cost?

The cost for an installation varies depending on the supplier and the type of installation. Furthermore, the investment cost can vary strongly depending on several factors, such as the need for an extra digestate storage tank, the distance of the manure pit to the AD plant, the need for eventual extra pretreatment steps, ... Quotations can be requested based on the required electrical power installed for your installation. When calculating the investment cost, it is important to take into account subsidies. These might vary over the year and in several countries, so it is recommended to look for the latest available information on this.

6.1.5. What are the most important yearly revenues?

The most important yearly revenue is the production of local, renewable energy, preventing the need to purchase it. When using a CHP, both electricity as well as heat will be produced, reducing the amount of electricity and heat needed from the grid. This revenue depends on the cost of electricity - which is highly variable - and the type of fuel used to produce heat. Using your own produced energy as much as possible is important instead of injecting it on the grid, since it costs more to take electricity off the grid

¹⁴ The electric efficiency of the CHP is on average about 30% and the methane content varies between 50% and 60%

than you receive to inject it on the grid. Also, certificates, grants, or other support mechanisms could be important yearly revenues, but these can vary from country to country.

6.1.6. *What are the most important yearly expenditures?*

The most important yearly expenditure is the installation's maintenance cost, which depends on the size and type. A maintenance contract is often set up between the farmer and the technology provider. It is important to highlight that the operation of a biogas plant also requires some time, on average about 30 minutes a day or 180 hours a year.

6.1.7. *What is the return on investment?*

The return on investment can be calculated by dividing the net investment cost by the yearly profit. The net investment cost is the investment cost of the installation minus eventual subsidies. The yearly profit is calculated as the yearly revenue minus the yearly expenditure.

6.2. GOOD PRACTICES FOR REUSE OF THE PRODUCED DIGESTATE

Inherent to AD and subsequent biomethane production, is the production of digestate. This nutrient-rich product could be used as a fertiliser, but it is important to consider some points of attention when applying this in the field. Therefore, Vlaco, Inagro, ILVO, UGent, VCM, Biogas-E and Febiga - all Flemish organisations working on biogas and/or nutrient recovery - produced a handbook of good practices when using digestate as a fertiliser. It can be accessed (in Dutch) via https://vlaco.be/sites/default/files/generated/files/page/code-goede-praktijk-duurzaam-gebruik-van-digestaat_0.pdf. Next to this, two hands-on (Dutch) brochures were also published: one for operators of AD plants¹⁵ and one for farmers¹⁶. The following paragraphs provide a summary of these good practices, which are necessary to take into account when applying digestate in Flanders. However, these good practices are applicable in all countries when using it as a fertiliser.

6.2.1. *Organic fertilisers*

Digestate products are sustainable organic fertilisers that can be put to beneficial use in agriculture. Their quality is highly regulated in Flanders. The strict standards are based on a dynamic model in which long-term application is simulated. Therefore, the risk of contaminating the soil with digestate is extremely low, provided it is used sustainably. In this way, soil and plants benefit fully from these valuable fertilisers.

¹⁵ https://www.biogas-e.be/sites/default/files/2021-04/Folder_Duurzame%20afzet_Vergister.pdf

¹⁶ https://www.biogas-e.be/sites/default/files/2021-04/Folder_Duurzaam%20gebruik_Landbouwer.pdf

6.2.2. Quality

Traceability plays a key role in quality monitoring. It is important that the digestate being used complies with all the different legislation regarding marketing of digestate and that it is certified. In addition, it is also crucial to know the actual composition (*e.g.* NPK content, OM, DM, pH). Furthermore, analysis for presence of antibiotics, heavy metals, and microplastics is recommended. This way, digestate is a reliable product.

6.2.3. Variability of digestate

Often, there is a wide range of digestate products available. Therefore, it is recommended that suppliers, contractors, or agricultural advisors look for the product that best matches the other fertilisers used to fulfil the plant's needs. Also, it is important to always ask for correct and clear information about the composition of the digestate, which is essential to ensure sustainable use. This is a necessity since there is variability in composition of digestate products between digesters because of differences in operations and within a given plant. For example, the latter may be due to seasonal variations in delivered residues or differences in available heat when further processing the digestate (more or less drying and/or evaporation possible). The variability of digestate can be limited by performing on-time analyses of the input material, which will also increase the customer's confidence. Input streams should be as consistent as possible, not only to guarantee a constant composition of the digestate but also to optimise the performance of the AD system. Samples should be taken in a representative way. A summary of a range of digestate products can be found in Table 13.

Table 13: Overview of several digestate products

Digestate product	N Efficacy (%)	Sustainable use
Raw digestate	60	NPK fertilisation in spring
Liquid fraction of digestate	60	NPK fertilisation in spring
Solid fraction of digestate	30 (animal manure) or 60 (other fertiliser)	NPK fertilisation - recognition as slow release fertiliser
Dried digestate	30 (animal fertiliser) or 60 (other fertiliser)	NPK fertilisation - recognition as slow release fertiliser
Effluent of liquid fraction of digestate	100	Fast release K fertilisation
Mineral concentrate out of digestate	100	Fast release fertilisation

6.2.4. Sustainable fertilisation

Sustainable fertilisation with digestate is done by the 4R principle:

- **Right fertiliser:** a good fertilisation strategy requires knowledge of the N efficacy of your fertiliser. This can be known via the N_{\min}/N_{tot} ratio. The higher this ratio, the higher the N efficacy.
- **Right dose:** to follow fertiliser recommendations (based on soil analysis) as optimally as possible, you need to know the composition, nutrient ratio, and N efficacy of the fertilisers used. Ask for this info from the supplier of your digestate products. Search for the digestate product that, together with the other fertilisers used, can best fulfil the plant's needs. Therefore, four steps need to be followed:
 - o Step 1: Know the soil composition, including the available nutrients
 - o Step 2: Know the crop requirements
 - o Step 3: Choose the right digestate product
 - o Step 4: Know what is allowed from a legislative point of view. This could be variable in different countries and even regions.
- **Right moment:** In Flanders, each digestate product is classified into types according to the Flemish Manure Decree (1, 2 or 3). This classification determines the fertilisation time. More info on the application regime of the different types of digestate products in Flanders can be found on the VLM website¹⁷. This strict regulation can be a leading example for other regions aiming for sustainable fertilisation with digestate.
- **Right fertilisation technique:** Solid digestate products can be widely applied. Liquid digestate products are best injected to limit ammonia losses.

However, it is important to highlight that the 4R principle is not only valid for fertilisation with digestate, but for all types of fertilisers.

6.3. TIPS AND TRICKS FOR ANAEROBIC DIGESTION

Within the Operational Groups Pocketboer and Pocketboer 2 framework, a hands-on poster providing tips and tricks on farm scale AD was developed by Inagro, Boerenbond and Biogas-E. The full poster is available in Dutch¹⁸, but below is a summary of the most important points:

1. Desulphurisation of biogas is important to reduce corrosion. This can be done in several ways:
 - a. Using aeration and a sulphur net: Introducing a limited amount of air/oxygen allows bacteria in the reactor to convert hydrogen sulphide (H_2S) into elemental sulphur. Installing a sulphur net enhances desulphurisation.

¹⁷ <https://www.vlm.be/nl/themas/waterkwaliteit/Mestbank/bemesting/aanwenden-van-mest/aanwenden-van-specifieke-meststoffen/Paginas/default.aspx>

¹⁸ https://inagro.be/sites/default/files/media/files/2023-05/2021%20Tips%20and%20tricks%20posterversie_UPDATE_0.pdf

- b. External desulphurisation: If internal desulphurisation methods are insufficient, consider adding an external desulphurisation reactor between the reactor and the CHP, using carrier material soaked in digestate and air injection.
 - c. Activated carbon can be used as a polishing step to further remove H₂S via adsorption.
2. Dewatering of biogas: cooling of the biogas to remove condensate is beneficial for the biogas valorisation, ensuring the efficacy of the active carbon filter and protecting the CHP engine.
3. Oil replacement: regular replacement of motor oil, including draining old oil, replacing the oil filter, and refilling with specified oil will increase the life span of the CHP.
4. Mixing: utilising mixers in the reactor will ensure better gas release, microorganism contact with feed, and temperature distribution.
5. Foam control: implementing various techniques will prevent and treat foam formation in the reactor, addressing stress on microorganisms.
6. Feeding: Regular addition of fresh biomass is needed to maintain microbial activity, with daily amounts depending on the reactor volume and the desired HRT.
7. Temperature: Maintaining a constant and ideal mesophilic temperature range of 38-40 °C or thermophilic temperature range of 50-55 °C will create a constant environment for the microorganisms, using external digestion heat or heating systems connected to the CHP.
8. Maintenance: Regular maintenance is needed to ensure optimal operation, with operators handling basic tasks and technology providers for solving more complex issues.
9. Energy production vs. consumption: increasing self-consumption of the produced energy will strongly increase the profitability of investing in farm-scale AD.
10. Safety: Strict safety measures are important, including avoiding entry into manure storage or digestion facilities without proper respiratory protection or ventilation and ensuring someone is present with communication devices during operations.

7. CONCLUSION

Value4Farm is dedicated to decarbonising the agricultural sector by addressing local electricity, heat, mobility, residual bioresources, and land management needs. An exemplary approach towards achieving Value4Farm's goals lies in the AD of agroresidues, which often remain underutilised. To facilitate this, a protocol outlining best practices for managing existing residual crop streams and utilising digestate has been developed, with a focus on the Flanders region, while acknowledging the potential for similar studies in other areas.

In Flanders, various biomass residues, including (hydro)leek, horticultural waste (such as tomato, cucumber, and bell pepper), chicory residues, and manure, are identified as potentially interesting for AD. Initial assessments revealed an almost consistent year-round production of these agroresidues, a crucial factor for AD viability. Nevertheless, these biomass residues are not yet widely used as biogas feedstock, providing a significant future potential for energy production. Furthermore, the subsequent biomethane production from these biomass streams shows promise with a reasonable abatement cost (< 55 EUR per tonne CO₂ abatement).

The resulting digestate has the potential to be a good fertiliser, providing all the nutrients that were also available in the input feed but more mineralised and hence rapidly available for crops. Since digestate could vary throughout several plants and the year, good practices for using this fertiliser are important. Generally, it is advisable to follow the 4R principle of sustainable fertilisation (Right fertiliser, Right moment, Right dose, Right fertilisation technique).

However, it is important to highlight that before committing to AD investments, evaluating the need for extra processing steps (e.g. diminishing the biomass) or logistical issues, as well as the biogas potential of these biomass residues, is essential. Since some of these residues have a rather low biogas potential (e.g. chicory leaves), co-digestion with manure might be the most viable approach, although it should be noted that the resulting digestate is considered as animal manure as long as one drop of manure is entering the AD plant, eventually hindering the application of it in nutrient intensive regions. The agroresidues assessed within this deliverable are strongly linked to the region of Flanders, but it can easily be expanded with crops of importance in other regions.

To conclude, the protocol offers practical advice for farmers considering AD investments, empowering them with insights and strategies for sustainable agricultural energy production. These practical tips and tricks are applicable for farmers with an AD plants in all countries and regions.

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